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Paradoxes in the conservation of newness: the invention of an antipodean 'civic domain'

Conserving the new within the domain of heritage: drawing the battle lines

'As Nietzsche observed long ago, the moderns suffer from the illness of historicism. They want to keep everything, date everything, because they think they have definitely broken with their past. The more they accumulate revolutions, the more they save; the more they capitalize, the more they put on display in museums. Maniacal destruction is counterbalanced by an equally maniacal conservation (Latour, 1991:69).'

In contrast to the 1950s and '60s 'campaign for the present' – with its refusal of historical values, and belief in progress and change – we are now witnessing, in our cities, the re-emergence of architectural historicism through the actions of conservation (Donzelot, 1900: pp. 16-28). Contemporary practices of architectural conservation attempt not only to preserve built fabric, but also to overlay coherent historical interpretations and narratives over existing urban contexts. In the case of Australia, the scripting of heritage narratives is orientated towards imperial and colonial artefacts, buildings and places. And although Australian cities were largely re-written within the modernist era of mid twentieth-century expansion, this vital internationalist episode in the story of antipodean urban development is now often edited out of, or seen as at odds with local historical narra-

tives of place. Precipitated by the general demise of late modernism, as elsewhere in the world, the conservation and commemoration of aged things, places and stories has been re-figured as the panacea for 'recovery' from a perceived condition of historical and contextual amnesia. It is within this climate of colonial historicism that the battle for the conservation of the modern Council House building has been waged in Perth over the last decade.

In describing the award winning design for the Council House competition in 1959, the national competition jury stated that of all the sixty one entries, it immediately and unanimously recognised this design as 'a direct and satisfactory solution ... being capable of development into a most dignified and efficient Town Hall.' It was further added: 'It is characterised by a remarkably simple solution to a complex problem' (The Architect, 1960:19). While a local news editorial of 1963 wrote: 'Already hundreds of visitors have praised the architectural qualities of the building and its garden environment. Council House has become the envy of other cities. And already Perth people were proud of the building which will soon be the centre of the city's administration system' (The Sunday Times, 1963:46). The English *Architectural Review* of 1964 predicted that the completed building 'should constitute one of the most satisfactory civic buildings in the commonwealth ... a proud symbol of the economic, civic and cultural bustle of a city that is currently one of the key growth-points of the Australian way of life' (The Architectural Review, January 1964: 54). (Figure 1)

Fig. 1 – Competition Drawings, Howlett and Bailey, 1960 – Elevation/Section sheet 7.

Despite these early accolades, by the late 1980s, Council House had dramatically fallen from grace in the eyes of the local public and politicians. It now found itself sited within an invented heritage domain, encompassing a gardened precinct and a collection of significant colonial public buildings

including: the old Supreme Court of 1837; the new Supreme Court of 1902; the site of Government House, (first built in 1835, and re-built between 1864 and 1899); the Deanery of 1859; late colonial government buildings spanning 1874 to 1902; and, the St George's Cathedral of 1870. While some of these institutions are still used for their intended function, others now bereft of their former purpose, are entrusted to public heritage guardians. Surrounded by this colonial heritage, the modern Council House was now perceived as troublesome and redundant - out of context and "in the wrong place at the wrong time". The then Minister for Planning commented: 'I think my vote would go with preserving the integrity of the domain as it was, and the intrusion of Council House has to be recognised' (The West Australian, 1994:56). The building was further vehemently denigrated by some as a belligerent monument to modernist 'reductivism' (Colquhoun, 1989:218), and accused of breaking supposed continuous threads of tradition and history linking colonial origins to post colonial reconstructions. The physical fabric and facilities were also seen to be in need of major renovation. One representative of public opinion evaluated the building in the following terms in 1994:

'It is basically an unsuitable, out-dated piece of asbestos-riddled concrete, metal, wood and glass which communicates negative visions and thoughts in the minds of most citizens through its spectacularly ugly appearance. I think it is just an ugly mal-formed piece of early 1960s junk that has no special use and which not only does not stand above other man-made structures as a work of architecture, but which is also an extraordinarily bad example of a very ordinary man-made structure, and it is still occupying a prime position in our central place, in our forum, in our space (Achurch, 1994:19).'

With quiet yet surgical precision, it was proposed by a West Australian government planning authority that this seemingly mis-fitting modern monument be erased and replaced, in a metaphysical sense with a simulated integrity of colonial ancestry, and in a physical sense with the tempering patina of warm "quality paving" and picturesque landscaping. This proposed action reflected the agenda of recent Australian urban renewal schemes which have aimed for, not just the enhancement of the colonial, but also the occlusion and exclusion of modernism; its confronting brightness and reflectivity being cast as the spectre which eclipsed any sense of colonial past. As Alois Riegl had predicted, places of 'newness-value' which appear as 'stylistically out of key or

downright ugly in the view of the modern *Kunstwollen*, generate a demand for deliberate destruction (Riegl, 1982:49).

The government led proposal for demolition did not go unnoticed by the local architectural community. A campaign was mounted between 1993 and 1995 in favour of retaining Council House on architectural grounds. Architectural and conservation studies were commissioned. Arguments in favour of its retention sought to: establish the buildings national and international architectural value; to highlight the already eclectic composition of buildings in this area of Perth; to emphasise the economic value of the physical structure of the building; and, to expose the uninspired option of providing yet more open green space in a city which already has an overabundance of unused, open green spaces. Conservation reports subsequently controversially determined that Council House indeed had historical significance because the building's inception was associated with the Empire Games hosted in Perth in 1962, and because of its perpetuation of governmental functions already housed in the area. The award winning building was determined as architecturally significant within the urban-scape of Perth, and a relatively rare surviving exemplar of the International Style. Its intact design, both exterior and interior, was evaluated as displaying innovative use of technology, servicing, fittings and furnishings.

These conservation evaluations were still rejected by many, and regarded as too architecturally focused on the supposed merit of the one isolated building, rather than the potential value of the greater colonial domain. An antagonistic community dialogue of public versus professional opinion grew, and was played out in the press and on-site rallies. (In one public forum the local architectural body was described as a 'self-interested' minority.) However, political and public opinions were ultimately swayed sufficiently to halt the demolition of Council House in 1995. Extensive restoration work began soon after, and the building and plaza has since been returned to a state of pristine newness – which Riegl identified as essential for any monument to modernism – and re-opened as the revitalised home of the Perth City Council in 1999. (Despite efforts, the building has still not been accepted on the National Heritage list.)

Designing newness

Perhaps the recent public rejection of this building – which had not so long before confidently captured the aspirations of a rapidly growing region – was due to the very adeptness of its design in importing and translating the strident lexicon of late civic modernism to Western Australia. The design was visibly opposed

to what had previously been accepted as appropriate architecture for institutional buildings. (A never realised second stage of the scheme radically entailed the part demolition of the neighbouring late colonial Supreme Court building to make way for a new Town Hall.) The building was somehow completely of its moment, capturing a resolute optimism in the sustained progress of the city of Perth in the early 1960s.¹ Stylistically, the building has been compared to Breuer and Nervi's Unesco building in Paris, late Mies van der Rohe works, and Bates, Smart and McCutcheon's MLC tower in Australia (Schwagger Brooks, 1993: pp.45-49). However, the Howlett and Bailey design can be regarded as an inflected and intentionally ambiguous reading of the late International Style. And these kinds of broad comparisons are only informative in a very general sense. I will, therefore, now back track a little to describe the building in more detail.

Set back from principal streets and corners, and sited within the open space of a civic square and casual gardens, Council House composes a discrete modernist object. The building thereby belies the traditional architectural concerns of front and back, and of a defined entry – typical of both its late colonial and contemporary corporate neighbours. This concern for the sculpting of space, as opposed to the creation of a contextual streetscape tableaux, reflects a far more general contrast between modernist and contemporary urban design sensibilities. Via the slightly elevated podium, edged by water fountains and ponds, one enters the forecourt through a Miesian-like porte-cochere, elevated by a series of white marble pilotis. Here the modernist strategies of openness and transparency are developed to Australian extremes; a fully glazed foyer filters views of the gardens and horizon beyond through a translucent and aqueous film of glazing and water. Transparency of both entry foyer and building skin reinforces the well worn modernist metaphor, or perhaps myth, of transparency which was applied in both the civic and private domain in Australia as elsewhere. In the civic context, the metaphor of transparency of visible government and minimal bureaucracy – approachable, without obstacles, and open to public scrutiny – was perhaps inaugurated in Terragni's Casa de Fascio and was re-interpreted later in many municipal buildings in Australia. While in the domestic context, the metaphor of transparency, as seen in the design of many Australian homes in the 1950s and '60s, reflected a modern personalisation of social responsibilities through the rendering of the private domain as visible and under public watch (Brown, 1995:159).

The light steel frame skeleton of Council House is clothed in a unique tiled brise-soleil which appears

to float proud of the sheer glazed skin. In striking contrast to adjacent solid and heavily grounded Victorian buildings, which seemed to devote all their architectural energy to occupying the empty ground of early colonial urban plans, here extraordinary efforts have been made to achieve a sense of elevation, weightlessness and thinness. At night the building is rendered shimmering and ephemeral. And it was this image of the building in darkness that seemed to capture public imagination. For example, one news report of the day commented: '... the building will be illuminated as also will the eight fountains and two large pools in the forecourt, presenting a picture composed of light, colour and depth.' (The Sunday Times, 1963:4) Whilst another report wrote: 'Already a city landmark by day ... an impressive beacon by night.' (The West Australian, 1962:40) And another; 'it has the effect of a glittering diamond in the city when night falls.' (The Daily News, 1962:41) (Figure 2)

Fig. 2 – Entrance foyer of Council House illuminated at night, Richard Waldendorp, 1963.

Upon entering the shade of the foyer, the slender white marble T-shaped pilotis visually reconfigure and demarcate the entry hall. Within the interior one views the architect's signature use of a burnt red colour for the lift shaft, and composition of monochromatic surfaces of black tiles, white marble and glass. Ascending the ten floor tower via the lift, access is gained to the open rectangular office floors, minimally enclosed by sheer floor to ceiling glazing. On the ninth floor, this orthogonal regularity masks a remarkable circular meeting chamber room framed in elegant timber cruciform mullions.

Paradoxes in the conservation of newness: the ongoing 'battle of the tenses'

Hilde Heynen has argued:

'Modernity now is no longer a matter of combat, the fight has been fought, now the issue is rather how to deal with a modernity that has implemented itself. This new stage of modernity brings along a certain historical consciousness which embraces modernity itself (Heynen, 1998:34).'

Although campaigns in the construction of modernist places may be over, the gaining of historical consciousness about the modernist period is not occurring without a fight. The battle-lines have rather been re-drawn; shifting forward to deal with the preservation of the remaining vestiges of modernism. Manfredo Tafuri has commented that the construction of any urban place always somehow involves the making of a battle site: 'That such a battle is not totalising, that it leaves borders, remains, residues, is also an indisputable fact.' (Tafuri, 1990: 8) The architectural battle of the tenses which has been enacted over the last decade in the conservation of the Council House - within the boundaries of a colonial heritage domain - is perhaps then the playing out of the aftermath of the original campaign to first construct such a stridently modern building on the site. As Bruno Latour has argued, the term modern, then, has not lost some of its potency or currency: '... the word is always being thrown into the middle of a fight, in a quarrel where there are winners and losers, Ancients and Moderns. "Modern" is thus doubly asymmetrical: it designates a break in the regular passage of time, and it designates a combat in which there are victors and vanquished (Latour, 1991: 10).'

As **appreciators** of architectural modernism, we are thankful for the retention of significant modernist buildings. However, there are paradoxes inherent in their preservation, which become all the more apparent through physical restoration, as opposed to historical documentation. Therefore, whilst the art historian Hans Belting has observed that the icons of modern art can now be comfortably admitted alongside traditional art as historical phenomena, (Belting, 1987:39) the conservation of modernist architecture presents a different case. For, in conserving architectural monuments, their symbolic potency may to some extent been retained in their very physicality. Yet this potency is also compromised, or lost, when ultimately recognised as historically valuable.

Alan Colquhoun interprets this deep dilemma inherent in the conservation of modernist architecture:

'In returning to the past we are turning to eternal aesthetic values. Yet it is precisely the use of past

forms that draws out attention to our remoteness from the time in which these forms were originally developed. We are reminded of the past as the past. The only way in which a building could make us feel that the values of architecture were eternal and not subject to historical change would be if its forms seemed "natural" to our way of life, in other words "modern" (Colquhoun, 1989: 240).'

We are indeed poignantly reminded of the end of modernism by the very acceptance of a building such as Council House into the heritage domain. And the original impetus to oppose, or stand outside of, existing historicist styles and traditions in order to frame the new, is thus being re-interpreted into an all-inclusive, historicist narrative of place-making. Perhaps conservation is thereby paradoxically dealing a final blow to the real existence of modernism; un-writing its potency, and preparing the way for its sedation.

Therefore, as the Australian art historian Bernard Smith has argued: 'Moderns, in short, have to learn to live within paradox (Beilharz, 1997:155).'

For modernism is time-bound. When assimilated fully into its community context, the values of modernity and exoticness diminish, and, concludes Smith, it becomes paradoxically archaic (Beilharz, 1997: 155). Latour further describes the incongruities of preserving the modern; for to be modern 'one can go forward, but then one must break with the past; one can choose to go backward, but then one has to break with the modernizing avant-gardes, which have broken radically with their own past (Latour, 1991: 69).'

The incongruities of Newness, History and Age

The complexities and incongruities of ascribing and conserving cultural values in things and places was premised, at the turn of the twentieth century, in the writings of Alois Riegl (Riegl, 1982: pp.21-50). In *The Modern Cult of Monuments*, Riegl questioned why some places were chosen to be preserved, and others destroyed or left to ruin. In answer, he constructed a typology of diverse historical and aesthetic values which, in comparison to other nineteenth century conservationists such as John Ruskin, moved on from the basic issue of whether to restore architecture or not, towards a more detailed study of the requirements for the preservation and commemoration of different types of historical and aged monuments and sites. Riegl established three related categories of modern commemoration: 'intentional' monuments; 'unintentional' monuments, retrospectively commemorated for their 'historical-value'; and, 'unintentional' monuments, retrospec-

tively commemorated for their 'age-value'. Riegl accurately predicted the ground-swell of admirers of age-value – an appreciation of the look of aged things and places – in the twentieth century. Yet he also championed the completely new, and the modern, as opposed to the historical copy. And through this discussion of contemporary values, in which functionality and the artistic expression of modernity were both appreciated, Riegl thereby added a fourth value of 'newness' (Riegl, 1982:39).

At the heart of Riegl's investigation of commemorative values was the exposure of inherent contradictions between these values of *newness*, *age*, and the *historical*: 'It would appear that we are facing an irresolvable conflict. On the one hand is an appreciation of the old for its own sake which objects to renovation; on the other an appreciation of the new for its own sake which attempts to remove all traces of age (Riegl, 1982:44).' Riegl thereby saw the temporal relationship of values as complex and contradictory, suggesting on the one hand that the new and the aged could be read as *complementary*; for 'age-value' and evidence of the natural passing of time and memory is dependent on its very contrast with the look of newness. On the other hand, Riegl qualified that things and places valued for their 'historical-value' and historical representativeness were in some ways *irreconcilable* with newness. For historical monuments, unlike aged monuments, must be preserved in a state of completeness so as to conserve their historical and commemorative value. The modern is thus here figured as interfering with the contemporary relevance of the historical, and interruptive of the assumed linear continuum of normative historical narratives. Riegl further elaborated that the historical, the aged, and the new require different conservation practices. He suggested that monuments embodying historical-value should be carefully *preserved*, and monuments of embodying age-value should ideally be left to fade and *decay*, and finally, in contrast again, 'flawless integrity' of form, colour, and detail of the modern should be vigilantly and pristinely *maintained*. Riegl wrote: 'In the new, signs of decay irritate rather than lend atmosphere.' He continued: 'We are disturbed at the sight of decay in newly made artifacts (premature aging) as we are at the traces of fresh intervention into old artifacts (conspicuous restoration). In the twentieth century we appreciate particularly the purely natural cycle of becoming and passing away (Riegl, 1982:32).' Indeed in many modernist buildings, as with Council House, their decay and weathering is seen as somehow inappropriate and ungainly, whereas when fully restored they are far better received by the general public.

The dependencies and contradictions of different commemorative values, as outlined by Riegl, have

been paralleled in the debate centred around the Perth heritage domain. For some arguments mounted for the retention of Council House appealed that the now aged modern monument would visually contribute to the eclectic collage of other buildings in the domain – also retained for their age-value. Whereas other arguments for its demolition were motivated by the belief that its flaunting presence invalidated the *historical* values of surrounding buildings, and obstructed the proposed curative operation of re-tying the colonial to the post colonial across the perceived rupture of the modern. Riegl's categorisation of values inherent in unintentional and intentional monuments thereby established that buildings and places are conserved and appreciated as both complementary, and yet also highly contradictory types of cultural markers within our contemporary urban collage. Therefore, as Forster has recognised, Riegl's thinking should not be reduced to the hope of a simple return to previous values, or banal eclecticism: 'On the contrary, he recognised that the contemporary concerns, the *Kunstwollen* of our epoch, profoundly determined our perceptions of the past: there is no objective past, constant over time, but only a continual refraction of the absent in the memory of the present (Forster, 1982:10).'

In conclusion, I return to our site of the 'battle of the tenses'. Hannah Arendt has illuminated, in *Between Past and Future*, how such cultural battles of the tenses are universal and inevitable (Arendt, 1961:7). She cites a parable by Franz Kafka in which a man is situated on a road, existing in a battleground between two antagonists which represent the force of the past pushing him from behind, and the force of the future blocking him from the front. As Arendt explains, what is significant about Kafka's parable is not only that the future, but also the past, is seen as a force to be reckoned with. The past is not perceived as a dead weight, nor does it pull one back; on the contrary, the past pushes forward in the guise of tradition and remembrance, and the future drives back antagonistically towards the past. The man on the road dreams of a moment in which he may be able to side-step this continuing temporal contest of the tenses, yet the battle lines are constantly shifting forward; pushed into the future by the growing force of the past. Each generation, suggests Arendt, must find its own space between the tenses, and 'ploddingly pave it anew' (Arendt, 1961:13).

In a sense this parable may be applied to the shifting ground of architectural history and conservation, upon which modernism is currently crossing the front-line of newness, progress and anticipation, backwards across the space of the present, towards the realms of historicism and memory. The status of

modernism is thus wavering uneasily upon contested territory; both representing the recent past, and on the verge of being embraced by the established heritage values of age and tradition. Hence, whilst modernism may have been famously characterised as a time of tumultuous transformations – when ‘all that was solid melted into air’ – this belief is being eclipsed by the postmodern longing for the fixing of historical continuities, the re-invention of traditions, and the simulation of permanences. For the conservation of modernist artefacts and places seeks to establish some form of temporal reconciliation; to ‘ploddingly pave anew’ the space of the present by bolstering the forces of tradition through the assimilation of modernism within its ranks. Yet, if we are to embrace the productive incongruities of newness, history, and age, conservation practices must resist the tendencies to generate totalising and historicising narratives. If not, we remain caught in the paradox that both the *demolition* of modernism in favour of the aged and the historical, and also the *restoration* of modernism, are both problematic or illusory solutions; both enhance the loss of what it was to be modern.

NOTES

¹ Hilde Heynen summarises three characteristics of the Modern as: firstly, being opposed to what has past; secondly, the embodying the new as opposed to the old; and, thirdly, signifying the momentary and the transient as distinct from the eternal and the immutable. However Hilde has also qualified this last characteristic as somewhat contradictory – embodying change as either transient, or a more resolute belief in change through sustained progress. See (Hilde, 1999: 9) and (Hilde, 1998: 31).

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